

1. Introduction

We present a high-resolution dataset spanning five years (February 2019 - September 2024), derived from daily physicochemical observations of surface waters in the Canary Basin. The data were collected by Surface Ocean Observing Platforms (SOOPs) installed on Voluntary Observing Ships (VOS) and moored oceanographic buoys. Two VOS conduct continuous monitoring along their regular routes: (1) the CanOA-VOS-1 aboard the Jona Sophie (formerly Renate P.), a freighter owned by Reederei Stefan Patjens GmbH & Co. KG and operated in Spain by Nisa Marítima, which covers the easternmost part of the Canary archipelago; CanOA-VOS-1 is a SOOP at the ICOS-ERIC network labelled as Class 1 station ES-SOOP-CanOA (2) the CanOA-VOS-2, utilizing the vessel Benchijigua Express, owned by the Fred Olsen Express company, which covers the westernmost part of the Canary archipelago.

Additionally, two moored oceanographic buoys provide valuable data at strategic coastal locations: (1) MORGAN-1 (Gando, Gran Canaria, 27.9296°N, 15.3646°W; González et al., 2023) and (2) ULA-2 (El Hierro, 27.6350°N, 17.9964°W). Sensors integrated into the oceanographic buoys (González et al., 2023) include an SBE 37-SI/SIP MicroCAT thermosalinometer that measures hourly sea surface temperature (SST) and salinity, a Cyclops-7F fluorescence sensor, an Optode 4835 oximeter, and a SAMI-pH pH meter that measure on a three-hourly basis. Both buoys are equipped with a PRO-CV ProOceanus pCO₂ monitoring system; MORGAN-1 also featured a Battelle system pCO₂ monitoring system (years 2020-2021) with a span calibration gas at 534.56 ppm, while ULA-2 includes a SAMI-pCO₂ sensor.

2. Dataset content

The dataset includes the following variables:

- “Date” (dd/mm/yyyy)
- “Time” (hh:mm:ss)
- “Latitude”
- “Longitude”
- “atmPress”: Atmospheric pressure (units: atm).
- “equTemp”: seawater temperature measured inside the equilibrator using a Hart Scientific HT1523 Handheld Thermometer.
- “intaketemp”: Sea surface temperature measured with a SBE38 thermometer at the main seawater intake of the vessel.
- “SSS”: Sea surface salinity measured with a SBE45 thermosalinograph just before the water supply to the equilibrator.
- “pCO₂sw”: Partial pressure of CO₂ in the sea surface (units: μ atm).
- “AT”: Total Alkalinity (μ mol kg⁻¹)
- “pH”: pH in surface seawater at in situ temperature computed in CO₂sys using as input variables AT and pCO₂sw.